

Synthesis of Some Transition Metal Chelates of Furfurylidene and 5-Nitrofurfurylidene Benzoyl Hydrazones as Potential Fungicides*

D. SURYA RAO and M. C. GANORKAR**

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

Manuscript received 7 May 1979, revised 30 September 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

Twelve complexes of the general formulae ML_n and $M'L_n \cdot 2H_2O$, where $M = Ni(II)$, $Cu(II)$ and $Zn(II)$ and $M' = Mn(II)$, $Fe(II)$ and $Co(II)$ and $L =$ Furfurylidene benzoyl hydrazone (FBHZ) or 5-Nitrofurfurylidene benzoylhydrazone (5-NFBHZ), have been synthesised and characterised. The Schiff bases coordinate through O, N atoms behaving as monobasic bidentate ligands, depending on the pH of the medium. These complexes have exhibited significant fungitoxicity against *Rhizoctonia solani*, the causative organism of sheath blight in rice and groundnut plants. Some of the chelates exhibited more toxicity when compared to Dithane, M-45, a commercial fungicide, screened in similar conditions. The fungitoxicity of the metal chelates was found to be in the following order $Cu > Ni > Fe > Zn > Mn > Co$.

In continuation of our earlier work^{1,2} on the potentiation of fungitoxicity of an active organic molecule through chelation with metal ions, here we report the synthesis and fungicidal screening of some transition metal complexes of furfurylidene benzoylhydrazone (FBHZ) and 5-nitrofurfurylidene benzoylhydrazone (5-NFBHZ). Acid hydrazides are well known for their antituberculous activity³, in addition to their extensive use in agriculture and industry⁴⁻⁷. Furfural and 5-nitrofurfural and their derivatives are reported for their fungicidal activities, in addition to other pharmacological uses⁸. With a view to use some Schiff base ligands derived from a hydrazide residue and furfural or 5-nitrofurfural, we have prepared FBHZ and 5-NFBHZ and their corresponding metal chelates. The transition metal chelates of Schiff bases derived from benzoylhydrazide with benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde have been reported⁹. Survey of literature reveals that very little information is available, on the complexing ability of FBHZ and 5-NFBHZ and fungicidal activities of metal chelates of these ligands. Hence it was thought worthwhile to study the complexing behaviour of the aforesaid Schiff bases with bivalent transition metal ions with particular reference to their stereochemistry and fungistatic evaluation. The toxic effect of an organic molecule will be diminished by the chelation of metal ions in some cases and it has been well established that in many cases augmentation of the toxic effect by metal chelation¹⁰. Further the introduction of nitro group into the heterocyclic moiety enhances the activity¹¹. 5-Nitrofurfurylidene benzoylhydrazone shows more fungitoxicity than furfurylidene benzoylhydrazone. These Schiff bases and their metal chelates were screened against

Rhizoctonia solani, the causative organism of sheath blight in rice and groundnut plants and pathogen for several other economically important crops and found to be potentially fungitoxic.

Experimental

The melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Furfural was freshly distilled before use. 5-Nitrofurfural diacetate was obtained from IDL chemicals, Hyderabad. pH measurements were carried out on a Elico pH meter Model LI-10T. Conductances of some of these complexes were measured in M/1000 DMF using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. The I.R. spectra of the ligands as well as their corresponding metal chelates were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer model-557 in the form of KBr pellets and in the range $4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The purity of the ligands as well as their metal chelates was determined by thin layer chromatography. Metal estimations of these complexes have been carried out by standard volumetric and gravimetric methods¹². Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of these compounds were determined by microanalysis.

(a) Preparation of furfurylidene benzoylhydrazone (FBHZ) :

Benzoylhydrazide was prepared by reported procedure¹³ and recrystallised from hot water. Benzoylhydrazide (0.01 mole) was dissolved in ethanol to which added freshly distilled furfural (0.01 mole) and the reaction mixture was kept on a

* Part of this work was presented at the symposium on "Metal-Organic & Organometallic Compounds and Their Uses in Chemical Synthesis", held at the Chemical Laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, from 3-6 October 1978.

** To whom all correspondence be made.

water bath for about thirty minutes. The product that separated out was filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried. Recrystallisation of the compound from methanol yielded pale brown shining needles. Yield 85%, m.p. 182°.

(b) *Preparation of 5-nitrofurfurylidenebenzoyl hydrazone(5-NFBHZ) :*

5-Nitrofurfural diacetate was hydrolysed by boiling with HCl (1 : 1) for about ten minutes and the solution was filtered. To the 5-nitrofurfural thus produced *in situ*, ethanolic solution of benzoyl hydrazide (0.01 mole) was added. The reaction mixture was digested on a waterbath for about twenty minutes. The resulting product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried. Recrystallisation of the compound from methanol yielded yellow shining needles, yield 90%, m.p. 220°. For the ligands the analytical data tallied well with the calculated values.

(c) *General procedure for the synthesis of metal chelates :*

The complexes were prepared by refluxing methanolic solutions of metal chlorides (0.01 mole) and ligands (0.02 mole and slight excess) for about 3-4 hours. The separated products were filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried in air first and then further dried at 110° in an air oven for about 2 hours. Some of these complexes were obtained in quantitative yield. Cu(II), Zn(II) complexes were isolated at the pH of ≈3 whereas Mn(II), Co(II), Fe(II) and Ni(II) complexes were isolated at the pH of 8-9.5.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are coloured, stable to air and moisture and decompose at higher temperature. All the metal complexes are insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in some common organic solvents, but dissolve in nitromethane, DMSO, DMF and 1,4-Dioxan. The negligibly low values of molar conductances (2.5 to 5.9 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹) of these complexes in M/1000 DMF suggest their non-electrolytic behaviour. Elemental analysis indicates that the metal to ligand ratio in these complexes is 1 : 2.

The infrared spectra are very revealing. In the I.R. spectra of the ligands the N-H stretching frequencies appeared around 3300 cm⁻¹ and ν(C=N) appeared around 1625 cm⁻¹. In the I.R. spectra of the complexes the absence of N-H frequency indicates the enolization of the hydrazine residue and deprotonation of the replaceable hydrogen, with the formation of M-O bond. The formation of M-O bond is further confirmed by the appearance of new peaks around 450-470 cm⁻¹. Other two

medium peaks in the spectra of the complexes around 350-390 cm⁻¹ have been observed and these are attributed to ν(M-N). The ν(C=N) in the complexes are lowered from 1625 to 1590 cm⁻¹, indicating the participation of nitrogen of the azomethine group in coordination. Because of the enolization of the ligands in solution, the complexes may exhibit two >C=N groups, but it is not possible to differentiate the two frequencies, due to the overlapping of other frequencies. The band around 1010 cm⁻¹, due to ν(N-N) shifts to the higher frequency in the complexes¹⁴ and this positive shift indicates the monodentate linking of >N-N< residue¹⁵. In the case of Mn(II), Fe(II) and Co(II) complexes a broad hump around 3400 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the presence of coordinated water. This is further confirmed by an additional peak around 825 cm⁻¹ in these complexes¹⁶. On the basis of elemental analysis, conductivity and infrared data, these complexes were given empirical formulae as ML₂ and M'L₂. 2H₂O, where M=Cu(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) and M'=Mn(II), Fe(II) and Co(II) and L=FBHZ or 5-NFBHZ.

Fungicidal Screening :

The fungitoxicity of the compounds was evaluated by agar plate technique¹⁷ against eight day old culture of *Rhizoctonia solani*, in potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium, using three sclerotial bodies in each petri plate. The number of replications in each case was three.

The following compounds were used for the fungicidal screening *in vitro*.

1. Furfurylidene benzoylhydrazone and 5-nitrofurfurylidene benzoylhydrazone.
2. Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) chelates of FBHZ and 5-NFBHZ.
3. Zinc ion+Manganese ethylene bis dithio carbamate (Indofil) Dithane, M-45 (75%WP).

The percentage inhibition by these compounds is recorded in Table 1.

$$\% = \frac{C - T}{C} \times 100$$

where C=diameter of the fungus colony in control plates after 96 hours, T=diameter of the fungus colony in treated plates after 96 hours.

All metal chelates exhibited significant fungitoxicity at 250 ppm but FBHZ and 5-NFBHZ showed activity at 500 ppm also. It is interesting to observe that some of the metal chelates exhibited more fungitoxicity when compared to Dithane, M-45, a commercial fungicide. The fungitoxicity has varied with metal ions and Cu(II) chelate has

TABLE 1—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING ; AVERAGE % INHIBITION AFTER 96 HOURS ;
 Organism : *Rhizoctonia solani*, Medium : PDA

Compound No.	Molecular formula	Concentrations used in ppm						
		10	25	50	100	200	250	500
1.	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₈	—	—	15.8	30.2	50.1	66.2	84.7
2.	MnO ₂ .H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆	5.1	11.9	24.5	44.7	75.9	100	100
3.	FeC ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆	6.2	15.1	36.0	49.5	79.3	100	100
4.	CoC ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆	4.9	10.8	22.8	42.4	73.1	100	100
5.	NiC ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	7.8	19.2	38.3	62.5	80.0	100	100
6.	CuC ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	8.1	20.9	40.1	67.5	98.0	100	100
7.	ZnO ₂ .H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	6.8	14.4	28.9	48.1	78.7	100	100
8.	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄	—	6.7	21.9	40.1	65.8	80.3	98.7
9.	MnO ₂ .H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₁₀	7.0	15.8	32.4	60.6	95.8	100	100
10.	FeC ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₁₀	8.1	19.2	40.3	65.4	99.3	100	100
11.	CoC ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₁₀	6.8	14.7	30.2	58.3	93.0	100	100
12.	NiC ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈	9.6	22.1	46.2	78.4	100	100	100
13.	CuC ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈	10.0	24.8	48.0	83.5	100	100	100
14.	ZnO ₂ .H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈	7.6	18.3	36.8	64.0	98.6	100	100
15.	Dithane, M-45 (Agricultural Fungicide)	7.9	18.6	37.1	64.7	98.8	100	100

exhibited maximum fungistatic activity. The above study clearly indicates that the metal chelates would be also more useful for fungicidal screening *in vivo*. The fungistatic activity of the metal chelates was found to be in the following order Cu > Ni > Fe > Zn > Mn > Co.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. T. Navaneeth Rao, Head, Department of Chemistry, for providing laboratory facilities, to Dr. K.S.R. Krishna Mohan Rao for his personal interest and to Dr. V. T. John, Senior Plant Pathologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (ICAR), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, for his encouragement. The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Dr. B. L. Subba Rao (AICRIP), for fungicidal screening of the compounds. The award of a Junior Research Fellowship by U.G.C. New Delhi, to one of the authors (D.S.R) is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- D. SURYA RAO, M. C. GANORKAR, B. L. SUBBA RAO and V. T. JOHN, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Letters*, 1978, 1, 402.
- G. VENKAT REDDY, D. SURYA RAO and M. C. GANORKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in Press).
- COLEMAN, *Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1954, 64, 1062.
- K. NAGANO, H. TSUKHARA and TAMURA, *Z. Chem. Pharm. Bull. Tokyo*, 1964, 12, 1198.
- R. C. AGARWAL and B. PRASAD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 1183.
- R. C. AGARWAL and B. PRASAD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 728.
- R. C. AGARWAL, B. PRASAD and B. N. YADAV, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 899.
- H. KALA and D. AUSBORN, *Pharmazie*, 1971, 26, 121; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 295.
- A. SYAMAL and K. S. KALE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16, 46.
- ADRIEN ALBERT, *Selective Toxicity*, (Chapman and Hall, London), 1973, 368, 370.
- K. VENKATESWARA RAO, I h.D. thesis, Osmania University, 1977.
- A. I. VOGEL, *Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, (I ongmans, London), 1968.
- L. GATTERMANN and H. WIRLAND, *Laboratory Methods of Organic Chemistry*, (Macmillan, London), 1963, 153.
- R. C. AGARWAL and K. K. NARANG, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 1413.
- A. BRAIBANTI, F. DALLVALLE, M. A. PELLINGHELL and LAPORATI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1430.
- K. NAKAMOTO, *Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds*, (Wiley Interscience), 1972, 166.
- J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 11, 357.